

APPLICATION OF MINERAL AND ORGANIC-MINERAL COMPOSTS TO AGRICULTURAL CROPS

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В условиях староорошаемых светлых сероземов при возделывании хлопчатника в короткоротационном севообороте принимаемых органо-минеральный компост (15 т/га) N-150, P-100, K-75 кг /га под озимую пшеницу и повторная культура соя оказывают положительное последствие на рост, развитие и продуктивность хлопчатника.

Ключевые слова: Озимая пшеница, повторная культура – соя, органо-минеральный компост, хлопчатник, урожай хлопка-сырца.

Enter. Increasing soil fertility in farming is directly related to the rate and proportion of mineral fertilizers, the use of organic fertilizers, the widespread use of crop rotation, and the introduction of advanced agrotechnologies that save land and water resources. We know that the use of the right agrotechnologies in the cultivation of plants is not only one of the main factors of obtaining a high yield, but also the production of quality products, proper nutrition and human health. We can say that man and our nature are in harmony. As the first link in the human chain, plants serve as the main source of proteins, fats, vitamins and biologically active substances for humans and other animals. Adequate plant nutrition leads to the need for synthetic food additives. Therefore, scientifically based use of organic mineral fertilizers in agriculture is of great practical importance.

Literary review. There are a lot of works have been doing for applying organic-mineral compost and yield agricultural crops. In this direction a lot of scientists had

done several works. They are Iminov Abduvali Abdumannobovich, Tursunhodjayev Z.T., Bolkunov A.S, Mirzahonov K.M, Umarova P and so on.

Research methodology. In this article analysis and synthesis, abstract-logical thinking and comparison methods were used.

In Uzbekistan, large-scale measures are being taken to efficiently use the available land and water resources for the fullest satisfaction of the population's needs for food and other types of agricultural products, as well as the production of raw materials for the industry, an annual uninterrupted, two-three-fold high-quality harvest, as well as an increase in the volume of products obtained. [1-2].

In this regard, when introducing short crop rotation systems on irrigated lands, the main attention should be paid to the cultivation of cereals, legumes, and vegetable crops that contribute to the preservation and increase of soil fertility and the provision of food to the population, their cultivation as secondary and catch crops with the use of organo-mineral composts.

Analysis and Results. All these issues together with efficient land use are urgent tasks [3-5]. Our experiments were carried out "Omad-97" with a short-rotation crop rotation of 1: 1 (winter wheat + repeated soybean culture: cotton), the aftereffect of the previously introduced organic-mineral compost (15 t / ha) and the effect of soybeans on fertility were studied soils and cotton productivity in the Andijan. On the control variant, N-180, P₂O₅-125, K₂O-90 kg / ha were used.

The soil under the experiment is light gray soil, medium loamy in texture, groundwater occurs at a depth of 4-5 m.

The studies were carried out in time and space (each year at a different site). The cotton variety Andijan-36 was cultivated. The following types of fertilizers were used: ammonium nitrate (N 33-34%), superphosphate (N 5-6%, P₂O₅-32%), potassium chloride (K₂O-60%). Organic-mineral compost was prepared on the basis of cattle manure and 10% NKFU (nitro- phosphate) and stored in piles for 4 months. In the fall, before sowing winter wheat, it was introduced into the soil according to the experimental scheme. It contained total nitrogen - 0.5%, phosphorus - 0.28%, potassium - 0.7%.

Before laying the experiment, the soil contained: total humus in soil layers 0-30 and 30-50 cm, respectively, 1.068-0.648%, nitrogen 0.106-0.086%, phosphorus 0.193-0.071%, potassium 1.67-1.56%, N- NO₃ -17.5-6.6; P₂O₅ 27.6 - 12.6 and K₂O-190-130 mg / kg soil.

Phonological observations carried out on August 1 showed that in the variant where cotton was cultivated after winter wheat (1-background) with the introduction of N-150, P₂O₅-100, K₂O-75 kg / ha, the height of the main stem was 90.8 cm, the number of sympodial branches 11.2 pcs., boxes (September 1) 10.1 pcs., including

opened 2.8 pcs. Application against this background on cotton N-200, P₂O₅-140, K₂O-100 kg / ha led to a further improvement in the growth, development of plants, and the above data, respectively, amounted to 92.8 cm, 12.1; 11.0 and 2.9 pieces, which is 2.0 cm, 0.9; 0.9 and 0.1 pcs. more in comparison with the 1st variant of experience. With an increase in the norms of mineral fertilizers to N-250, P₂O₅-175, K₂O-125 kg / ha, no significant differences were observed between the options.

It was found that when using only mineral fertilizers on winter wheat in the amount of N-180, P₂O₅-125, K₂O-90 kg / ha on cotton, the optimal rates were N-200, P₂O₅-140, K₂O-100 kg / ha. It should be noted that similar results were also obtained in other experiments.

On the second background, created on winter wheat by introducing N-180, P₂O₅-125, K₂O-90 kg / ha and 15 t / ha of organic-mineral compost when applied to cotton N-150, P₂O₅-100, K₂O-75 kg / ha the height of the main stem of cotton was 93.5 cm, the number of sympodial branches was 13.1 pcs. and boxes (1.09) 11.2 pcs., including opened 3.5 pieces. These indicators, in comparison with the parallel (1) version of the 1st background, were respectively 2.7 cm, 1.9; 1.1 and 0.7 pieces, which is explained by the improvement of soil fertility after the introduction of organic-mineral compost (15 t / ha) on winter wheat. Against this (2) background, when applying fertilizers on cotton in the amount of N-200, P₂O₅-140, K₂O-100 kg / ha, the height of the main stem was (1.08) 95.2 cm, the number of sympodial branches 14.1 pcs., Bolls (1.09) 12.1 pieces, including open 3.8 pieces, which is 1.7 cm, 1.0; 0.9 and 0.3 pcs. more in comparison with the 4th option.

On the third background of the experiment, where N-180, P₂O₅-125, K₂O-90 kg / ha (without compost) were applied on winter wheat and a second crop was cultivated - soy, when N-150, P₂O₅-100, K₂O- 75 kg / ha (7-var.), At the end of the growing season the height of the main stem was 94.5 cm, the number of sympodial branches 14.1 pcs., Bolls (1.09) 13.6 pcs., Including open 3.8 PC. These indicators were more, respectively, by 3.7 cm, 2.9; 3.5 and 1.6 pcs. in comparison with the parallel versions of the 1st background, and the 4th version (2nd background) by 1.0 cm, 1.0; 2.4 and 0.3 pcs.

It was revealed that in order to improve the growth and development of cotton, it is necessary not only to introduce organic-mineral compost for winter wheat, but also to cultivate a re-culture of soybeans.

It was determined that relatively high experimental values were obtained on the 4th background, where N-180, P₂O₅-125, K₂O-90 kg / ha + 15 t / ha organic-mineral compost were introduced on winter wheat and a repeated soybean culture was cultivated. Against this background, when using N-150, P₂O₅-100, K₂O-75 kg / ha on cotton (10-var.), The height of the main stem was (1.08) 98.0 cm, the number of

sympodial branches 15.2 pcs., Bolls 14.1 pieces, including 3.9 disclosed pieces. These indicators were more, respectively, by 3.5 cm, 0.4; 0.5 and 0.1 pieces in comparison with the 7th variant of the experiment, where the repeated culture of soybeans was cultivated, without the introduction of organic matter.

Against this 4th background, where the above-mentioned norms of mineral fertilizers and organic-mineral compost were applied on winter wheat, and a second crop was cultivated - soybeans, when N-150, P₂O₅-100, K₂O-75 kg / ha were applied on cotton (10- option) the yield of raw cotton on average for 3 years amounted to 39.8 c/ha, the increase from the action of soybeans was 6.4 c/ha, from the aftereffect of organic-mineral compost 2.0 c/ha, and from the combined effect of compost and soybeans 8.0 c/ha.

It should be noted that these indicators were relatively high in comparison with the rest of the test options.

It was found that with a short-rotation scheme (1: 1) crop rotation, the application of mineral fertilizers N-180, P₂O₅-125, K₂O-90 kg / ha and 15 t / ha of organic-mineral compost improves soil fertility, increases the productivity of winter wheat, as well as repeated soybean crops, which ultimately lead to a greater accumulation of root and crop residues, and also creates optimal nutritional conditions for the subsequent cotton crop.

In conclusion, we can say that in the conditions of light gray soil of the Andijan region, in order to increase soil fertility and productivity of cotton crop rotation, it should be applied against the background of mineral fertilizers and organic-mineral compost (15 t / ha) for winter wheat, as well as to cultivate repeated legumes soybeans.

The list of used literatures

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